

Scope & Topics

International Journal of Biomedical Engineering and Science (IJBES) is a peer-reviewed, open access which focuses on the latest advances, applications and future trends in the area of Biomedical Engineering. The journal documents practical and theoretical results which make a fundamental contribution for the development of Biomedical Engineering and science.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following

- Biomedical Electronics
- Bioinformatics of Diseases
- Bioinstrumentation
- Biomaterials
- Biomechanics of injury and wound healing
- Biomechatronics
- Biomedical Intelligence & Clinical Data Analysis
- Bionanotechnology
- Bionics
- Biophysics
- Cellular, Tissue and Genetic Engineering
- Clinical BioChemistry
- Computational Systems Biology
- Immunology
- Injury Prevention and Health Protection
- Medical Engineering Systems & Applications
- Medical Robotics
- Neural Engineering
- Orthopedic Bioengineering
- Rehabilitation engineering
- Social and preventive medicine
- Sport and exercise medicine
- Systems Physiology
- Toxicology

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail ijbesjournal@airccse.com. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : December 01, 2018**
- Notification : January 01, 2019
- Final Manuscript Due : January 09, 2019
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

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